

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP2 - Pilots' implementation and Open Call COESO pilots' blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform

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Deliverable 2.2

Pilots' Hypotheses.org blogs

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Summary

The deliverable D.2.2, “COESO pilots’ blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform”, presents the current implementation of the COESO pilots’ blogs on Hypotheses.org and the support pilots’ teams receive for managing them (Task 2.7). The deliverable introduces Hypotheses.org, the academic blogging platform hosting the pilots’ blogs (Part II) and the possibilities the platform provides for communicating about participatory research in the social sciences and the humanities (Part III). It then describes the support provided to the pilots’ teams (Part IV) and finally provides an overview of the first five COESO pilots’ blogs (part V).

This deliverable, due in December 2021, relates to the first five pilots’ blogs implementation on the [Hypotheses.org](https://hypotheses.org) platform; the next five pilots will be selected in the first quarter of 2022.

I. The COESO project, its pilots and their blogs

The [COESO project](#) (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) is a 3-year participatory research project, coordinated by the [École des hautes études en sciences sociales](#) (EHESS) and [OpenEdition Centre](#), funded by the European Commission through a Science with and for Society grant, and supported by the [OPERAS research infrastructure](#). The project develops the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA), a collaborative online platform for knowledge production and sharing. The COESO project also collaborates with research funding organizations to enhance financial support for citizen science in the social sciences and the humanities. It will moreover explore the frontiers of innovation in the social sciences and humanities’ public engagement through mutual learning and transmedia writing experimentations. Furthermore, to measure the quality of collaboration between the researchers and the engaged stakeholders involved in the pilots, COESO will design a self-assessment tool: “cooperation analytics”.

COESO serves as a meeting point between various European communities: the social sciences and humanities community, the citizen science community, as well as the open scholarly communication community. As a bridging endeavour, COESO will take stock of existing communities such as the [Hypotheses.org](https://hypotheses.org), dedicated to academic blogging in the social science and the humanities, and the [EU-Citizen.Science](#) community, gathering citizen science advocates, practitioners and researchers from all over Europe.

At the heart of COESO are ten citizen science pilots, representing a variety of social sciences and humanities disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The initial five pilots address specific societal issues: mass tourism, education and gender, resilient societies, fight against crime, societal changes and migration. Five more pilots will be selected during the second year of the project implementation (2022).

The international academic platform Hypotheses.org, based on the free and open-source content management system WordPress, will be the main communication channel to the public for the COESO project and its pilots. The pilots’ blogs will also be used as a research tool and as a

research communication tool.

The pilots' blogs will enhance the public outreach of the pilots themselves, and will also serve the VERA onboarding strategy, following two-stages:

1. Each pilot will have its own Hypotheses.org blog, will benefit from specific support from a dedicated community manager and specific actions of communication will be directed towards the targeted engaged community;
2. An onboarding VERA widget will be implemented into Hypotheses.org in the third year of COESO's implementation, inviting Hypotheses.org researchers to join VERA users by promoting VERA projects. As it will be a WordPress widget, it will also be available more largely for all WordPress users.

Through the strong connection with Hypotheses.org, VERA will combine citizen science and open science by relying on the Hypotheses.org blogging platform to openly disseminate the results of the research projects.

II. Hypotheses.org platform presentation

An open scholarly communication instrument fitted for the social sciences and the humanities

Hypotheses.org is an international academic blogging platform dedicated to the social sciences and the humanities (SSH), integrated to the OpenEdition infrastructure¹, and an EOSC service. It provides open access to research electronic notebooks (blogs) in the SSH domains. Hypotheses.org is unique for size and scope, as a dedicated platform for renewing scholarly communication in the social sciences and the humanities through the practice of open blogging. The very idea of research notebooks, and their effectiveness for research practises within the SSH domain, is at the core of the foundation of Hypotheses.org and the framing of academic blogs as “electronic research notebooks”. Furthermore, Hypotheses.org blogs, which mix the academic practice of personal writing in research notebooks with the new practice of public writing on the web, are *open* electronic notebooks — using a multimedia format that leads to innovative possibilities for open scholarly communication².

Hypotheses.org consists of more than 5500 active blogs (where at least one blogpost has been published in the last 2 years); 17 million visits were registered in 2020³. Through Hypotheses.org,

¹ OpenEdition is a comprehensive digital infrastructure for academic communication in the humanities and social sciences. It brings together four complementary platforms focused respectively on journals (OpenEdition Journals), book series (OpenEdition Books), research blogs (Hypotheses) and academic events (Calenda). With its status as a national research infrastructure, OpenEdition is supported by OpenEdition Center, a CNRS Service and Research Unit (USR 2004), and by Aix-Marseille University, the EHESS and Avignon University.

² See Marin Dacos and Pierre Mounier, *Les carnets de recherche en ligne, espace d'une conversation scientifique décentrée*, in *Lieux de savoir*, vol.2, *Gestes et supports du travail savant*, Albin Michel, 2010. Available online on HAL archive ([sic_00439849](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00439849))

³ Data registered at the end of December 2020.

not only appointed researchers, but also PhD students, librarians or archivists, are invited to share about their research and professional learnings and experiences within academia.

The researchers engaged in scholarly communication through Hypotheses.org form a community open to, and experimenting with, new forms of academic communication: international, interdisciplinary and open to society. They communicate with their peers and with society openly, without delay and interactively, on any part of their research projects’ activities - field work, data analysis, seminar and conferences, results, etc.

The technical maintenance of Hypotheses.org is ensured by OpenEdition, which guarantees the safety and stability of the platform, allowing Hypotheses.org bloggers to focus on the content they create.

A multilingual and international platform

Born as a France based service in 2009, Hypotheses.org started its internationalisation in 2013 and today 41% of the produced content is in a language other than French, especially in English, German and Spanish. Of the 17 million visits in 2020, about 5.4 million came from regions outside the EU.⁴

Three linguistic communities are directly supported through dedicated teams: the French-speaking community, managed by OpenEdition, the German-speaking community managed by Max Weber Stiftung and the Spanish-speaking one, managed by the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED).

⁴ See the [OpenEdition Annual Report 2020](#)

The dedicated Hypotheses.org team, which includes the international team of community managers, and the community manager dedicated to supporting COESO participatory blogs, ensures training and counsel to the bloggers, on both technical aspects and editorial ones, as described more in detail in Part V.

After this overview of the Hypotheses.org platform, we will now outline how participatory research projects are represented in this academic open blogging platform.

III. Participatory research and academic blogging

As previously stated, the researchers engaged in scholarly communication through Hypotheses.org form a community open to and experimenting with new forms of open scholarly communication: international, interdisciplinary and open to society. Nonetheless, introducing a specific research practice such as participatory research — involving non-academic stakeholders in every phase of the research process — to a well established academic community with a strong identity and with established quality control processes, is a challenge that needs specific support. The COESO pilots’ community management confronts this challenge, relying on the experience of the Hypotheses.org team, by supporting researchers to enhance their participatory research practises through academic blogging.

Besides COESO pilots’ blogs, Hypotheses.org already hosts blogs in support of participatory research and citizen science projects involving the social sciences and the humanities. These blogs are used either:

- as **a reflexivity or networking space dedicated to citizen science practice**, like the German blog

"Bürger Künste Wissenschaft" (<https://bkw.hypotheses.org/>) taking over from a 2015 conference, collecting examples and experiences about citizen science practises within the cultural and the humanities sectors, and gathering resources for citizen science in the SSH. Or like, the research network PARCS (<https://parcs.hypotheses.org/gdr-parcs>) aiming at promoting the sharing of participatory research tools between researchers and civil society actors; their blog is one of the project's spaces to share collective resources.

- as **a space for dissemination of information related to a particular participatory project**. It's the case of the project *Les urbaines* (<https://urbaines.hypotheses.org/>), started in 2013, an action-research project in a town near Paris, Gennevilliers, to understand the gendered uses of public space in the urban context. It brought together researchers in geography, architecture, urban planning and political science, as well as artists, actors, writers, photographers and graphic designers, and the inhabitants of the town. Another example is the TAPLA project (<https://tapla.hypotheses.org/>), about the rediscovery of urban "adventure playgrounds", the "*terrains d'aventure*", in French, that are built and experienced as places where the children themselves build their own play space by playing (in contrast to playgrounds built by adults for children). In their Hypotheses.org blog, the project members showcase their action-research activities.

- as **a support for ongoing research** in the field, where **partners share results, analyses and thoughts through the blog**, between themselves first, and for a larger audience. Examples of this use of the Hypotheses.org platform is the PLACES project (<https://places.hypotheses.org/>), where collaborations between SSH researchers and journalists were carried out, and of the Sigi-AI participatory project (<https://sigial.hypotheses.org/>), which aims at digitising, by the means of photos, seals kept in regional archives, at analysing them, enriching them with metadata and adding them to a national database.

We are highlighting here only those *blogs* that are specifically dedicated to participatory research and citizen science as a research practice within the social sciences and the humanities, but other examples of *single posts* on participatory research and citizen science are published on Hypotheses.org. And we wish to highlight two points: 1) the potential of Hypotheses.org to support and innovate around joint knowledge production endeavours involving different stakeholders in participatory research activities that tackle societal challenges (like gender issues in urban spaces, as shown with *Les Urbain.es*); and 2) the relevance of open scholarly communication in such endeavours.

These use cases of Hypotheses.org blogs for participatory research give us examples and ideas to build a tailored support service for the COESO pilots' bloggers.

IV. Working method for pilots' blogs support

As a first step, the support of COESO pilots in managing their blogs, takes stock of the methodologies already implemented by the Hypotheses.org team and the international community managers team. This includes sharing the already existing resources about the technical and editorial management of a Hypotheses.org blog, but also enhancing this

documentation with specific tips fitted for participatory research and citizen science projects.

As a second step, and in order to provide a larger outreach for the COESO pilots' blogs, the dedicated community management may go further and support the pilots' teams in exploring the possible links between their various mediums (e.g. existing websites or social networks they already use for the project purposes) from a transmedia perspective (as we will see in the next section).

Finally, the pilots' blogs' content is articulated with the COESO media environment. On Hypotheses.org, the COESO project itself has its own blog: <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>, where the project participants share news and insights from the ongoing research, and where specific pilots' news and activities are highlighted via a dedicated space (accessible via the "Pilots" tab).

Hypotheses.org communities support

Hypotheses.org support to its multilingual communities consists of three pillars: free trainings, free documentation, and dedicated mailing lists for the members of each linguistic community. In addition, the French-speaking community also has an open forum⁵.

The Hypotheses.org existing multilingual documentation facilitates the first steps on the platform for COESO pilots' bloggers. The Hypotheses.org general presentation above pointed out the platform's multilingual context (see Part. III); there are four resources hubs dedicated to help the bloggers of each linguistic community:

- French : <https://maisondescarnets.hypotheses.org/>
- English : <https://houseofblogs.hypotheses.org/>
- German : <https://bloghaus.hypotheses.org/>
- Spanish : <https://casadelosblogs.hypotheses.org/>

Source: screenshot "The house of blogs", 23th november 2021

⁵ See <https://support.hypotheses.org/>

For the pilots' teams that speak a language other than French, Spanish, or German, [The House of blogs](#) provides a *lingua franca* space, offering English documentation that the pilots' bloggers can access anytime. They will find tutorials and guidelines about best editorial practises, as well as news articles about the platform's evolution. For the French-speaking bloggers, [La maison des carnets](#) offers an online stepwise training.

These dedicated entry points for specific resources and training for Hypotheses.org, available in open access, are a basic need of the Hypotheses.org communities, even if Hypotheses.org is based on a multisite version of the well known and well documented content management system WordPress. Indeed, WordPress has been adapted to the security and stability needs of a thousands-blogs multisite - that implies limitations in terms of personalizations - and has also been to the specific needs and variety of editorial practises of the SSH academic community. An article on The House of blogs, ["Features"](#), familiarises users to some of the plugins currently active or inactive on Hypotheses.org.

For the specific needs of the COESO pilots teams, not covered by the already existing documentation, the dedicated community manager will produce a common document with frequently asked questions and answers. This document could also be used as a communication tool between them, possibly feeding the debate on blogging practises within participatory research projects. Indeed, the community manager's task is not only to answer the technical questions but also to suggest editorial solutions and invite the pilots teams to experiment with innovative communication practises that match their research goals. Finally, because the pilots' Hypotheses.org blogs are part of the larger media environment of each pilot-project, making relevant links between the different stakeholders' existing media seems a relevant strategy to enhance the outreach of the pilot projects.

This strategy includes multimedia, cross-media and transmedia approaches, as developed in the next section.

Multimedia, cross-media and transmedia approaches to the editorialisation of participatory research blogs

Multimedia content

The COESO pilots' bloggers are encouraged to explore multiple forms of expression in addition to text: visual, audio, audiovisual. Multimedia content enriches the blog narrative and widens the frontiers of an inclusive open scholarly communication. Pictures, images, and recorded sounds depict aspects of a project that the written words cannot: in this respect, audiovisual content is more likely to overcome linguistic barriers. Multimedia content can be raw data from the fieldwork or a rendering of results; the possibilities to use multimedia content are wide-ranging.

Cross-media

Cross-media projects are deployed across several types of media, possibly connected together, but providing the same information across each one of these different media. It is more about the translation of the same content into different technical media frameworks.

A cross-media strategy could be considered for the COESO pilot projects according to their existing websites, and especially if a transmedia perspective cannot be applied.

The transmedia perspective

A transmedia perspective involves a simultaneous thinking process on narratives and on mediums, based on how many sides of the story you want to tell, and on how many mediums you want to use. Authors and producers have to think from the beginning which story they want to tell on each medium. Transmedia principles follow the idea that the public should not find the same narrative on each medium, just translated, but discover different aspects of a same subject: this leads to taking into consideration the users' experiences, and to design specific paths users can follow across the various mediums.

To start building a transmedia path you may start by asking who could be interested in that specific matter? Someone interested in a subject can, for example, start by reading an article on a website, then follow a link leading to a documentary and then find, on the project's social networks, an event she could join. Another person, less interested, will only watch the documentary and stop there.

This specific way of understanding the “transmedia” logic has been elucidated by a *fan studies* researcher, Henry Jenkins, in his *Convergence Culture*.⁶ In this perspective, developing a transmedia strategy requires targeting a specific audience — the presumed most involved one— and designing a universe of narratives around a subject for them to browse through. The ultimate goal is to enable interactions with the users, allowing them to become actors in the universe of narratives that have been built.

Applied to COESO pilots projects, a transmedia perspective would allow to create links between the narrative pilots teams wish to create on their new Hypotheses.org blog, and the existing narrative they suggest on the current media they already manage (social media, websites or other media products). Thinking about the paths that a person interested in the pilots' subjects may take to explore issues like mass tourism, fight against crime or societal changes, means designing possible journeys they could follow between the Hypotheses.org blog and the other various media. What information could they find on the blog that broadens their knowledge? Is there room for the audience to interact with the pilots' team? Exploring the transmedia potentialities for the pilots' blog narratives seems particularly relevant for participatory research projects involving stakeholders from outside of academia who are already engaged with the public through existing media.

V. Presentation of the COESO pilots' blogs

In this section, we will present the blogs of the first five pilots involved in the COESO project. The presentations include a brief summary of the pilots' participatory research, the first approach with their open electronic research notebooks on Hypotheses.org and some questions they posed.

⁶ Henry Jenkins, *Convergence Culture: Where Old and New Media Collide*, New York University Press, 2006.

Pilot 1: Mass tourism's impact on urban communities

Pilot 1 project summary

Pilot 1 includes [CRIA](#), a research laboratory in social anthropology, and [ZERO](#), a Portuguese national NGO for the promotion of sustainable development: together they are creating the 'Lisbon Tourism Observatory'.

Concerned citizens, local authorities, and university affiliates—all in Lisbon's historical Santo António district—explore the social, economic and environmental challenges bred by mass tourism and develop strategies to promote dialogue and reduce tensions at the local level. These strategies could later be replicated to promote community engagement in other cities highly impacted by mass tourism, through the involvement of the inhabitants, local authorities, and policymakers.

“Cidade (In)visível” blog and its media environment

URL address : <https://civtur.hypotheses.org/>

Pilot 1's open electronic research notebook (blog) was launched in October 2021, and the blog's main language is Portuguese. Six articles were published between the launch on 30th November 2021. Pilot 1's core team is composed of CRIA researchers and a ZERO NGO activist, who is also a former SSH researcher. The core team will manage the blog and several members of ZERO and Santo António inhabitants involved in Pilot 1 activities will be invited to contribute to livening up the contents.

Pilot 1's team uses the Hypotheses.org blog to disseminate information about the project and to ensure good internal communication within the core working group. The blog is a space for sharing upcoming activities and information and for ensuring good follow-up of the research even for participants who are not involved in all the project activities.

During their fieldwork, the professional researchers recorded sounds, images and interviews, collected in particular during a group walk through Santo António, and they are planning to publish this material on the Hypotheses.org blog. The professional researchers also organised an online workshop for inhabitants about, which was recorded and will be available for those who could not attend.

On the technical side, among the WordPress themes made available by the Hypotheses.org team for users, they chose the Twenty Sixteen theme. As the home page, they use the common blogs dynamic page, which gives access to the latest published article.

The current concerns are mostly technical. One concern is mainly related to finding the best hosting solution for multimedia contents which cannot be hosted in the Hypotheses.org WordPress library. Because Santo António district inhabitants will be involved in the article writing, the second concern is about finding the best solution to properly showcase multiple authors metadata, giving proper credit to all contributors, ideally in a way that could be correctly harvested by search engines. WordPress plug-ins exist that are developed by the WordPress community, to allow a single WordPress blog showcasing multiple authors, but these solutions aren't fitted for multisite installations of WordPress managing thousands of blogs. Even if a

simple solution for giving credit to all contributors can be easily found by showcasing the information in the main text body, solving the issue of including credits as a specific and shareable metadata needs more complex developments.

The Pilot 1's partners, CRIA and ZERO, have their own institutional websites, but they aren't mobilising them for the COESO project purpose. The Hypotheses.org blog is their common medium for the Pilot 1 communication and dissemination. Nonetheless, their additional digital spaces could be included in a cross-media or transmedia strategy.

Pilot 2: Dancing Philosophy. Desire through dance and philosophy

Pilot 2 project summary

Pilot 2 includes the artistic company [Cadmium](#) and a team of two researchers and a research assistant from the [Université Polytechnique Haut-de-france \(UPHF\)](#).

This project engages a dancer-choreographer with a philosopher and uses technological tools to assist in connecting dance movements to thought and underlying philosophical notions.

As part of the project, Laban choreographic notation (a method for “writing dance”) is being added to MemoRekall⁷—a software for documenting creative processes that make it possible to enrich videos with notations, links, photos, and documents of various kinds.

The philosopher and the dancer-choreographer engage themselves in a skill-exchange in which the philosopher experiments body expression through dance and the dancer-choreographer faces a new practice of writing. They both experiment a new way to perform their artistic and intellectual practice, with the aim of developing an innovative pedagogical method. The project includes several dance workshops with engaged groups of children and adults, where this new methodology will be used.

“Dansophie” blog and its existing media environment

URL address : <https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/>

Pilot 2's open electronic research notebook was launched in October 2021, the blog's main language is French. Ten articles were published between the launch and 30th November 2021. All members of the Pilot 2 core team will manage the blog.

The Pilot 2 team uses the Hypotheses.org blog to explore various styles of writing for rendering their ongoing research, to test some work hypotheses⁸, to disseminate information about the project among other pilots to make further cooperation easier, to present the project to an external audience—especially the workshop participants— and to continue to engage with the community.

⁷ See <http://www.memorekall.com/home-en.php>

⁸ See for example the dance-notator blogpost about the possibilities for rendering body movement through the Laban Kinetography: Irénée Blin, “*Notation - première expérimentation*”, in *Dansophie blog*, 12 december 2021, <<https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/96>>.

During their fieldwork, they record videos, take photos, and sketch notes on paper or notebooks. Most of the material collected is stored on a secured server of the public research infrastructure Huma-Num, and can eventually be shared with the public after assuring it is compliant with GDPR regulations.

On the technical side, among the available WordPress themes for Hypotheses.org users, they chose the Twenty Sixteen theme. As the home page, they use the common blogs dynamic page, which features the latest published article.

From the editorial standpoint, the question of the “legitimacy” of non-academic authors contributing to an academic space has been raised as a concern and discussed by the artists involved in the project. Hypotheses.org application asks two conditions to be fulfilled in order to apply for opening an electronic research notebook on the platform: to provide a clear editorial and scientific project description, and that at least one of the leading editors of the blog has an academic affiliation. Participatory research projects fulfill these two conditions. Nonetheless, the rising of this question highlights the siloed condition of knowledge production, sharing and dissemination that practitioners and researchers may face, even when they engage in a joint research endeavor. Challenging the interprofessional boundaries on an open platform dedicated to scholarly communication, seems to be an interesting opportunity that both parties are happy to seize. Supporting the pilots’ teams also means encouraging them in this path.

Another editorial question raised is how to deal, on the same medium such as a blog, with a diversity of targeted audiences, that normally lead to adapted and diversified content. The question of the writing style is thus central for Pilot 2 participants: how can or cannot these styles be blended? How could they evolve, if any?

The Pilot 2’s partners, Cadmium and UPHF, have their own institutional websites, but they aren’t mobilising them for the COESO project purpose. The Hypotheses.org blog is their common medium for the Pilot 2 communication and dissemination. Some Pilot 2 members mobilise their personal social media accounts to engage their followers with the pilot’s activities or results. A cross-media or transmedia strategy, which utilizes all these communication resources, could be implemented—not only for outreach, but also to engage in participating in the various planned workshops.

Pilot 3: Social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia

Pilot 3 project summary

Pilot 3 includes a journalist from the European online magazine [Cafébabel](#) and an independent researcher from the [Crim’HALT](#) association, who is also a teacher at a public academic institution.

The project focuses on the practice of redistributing property confiscated from the Mafia to be used for public interest, and the research fieldwork is articulated with a “Solutions Journalism” perspective. The social allocation of confiscated properties, and in particular the study of the concrete impacts of the Italian law on the social uses of confiscated properties, is indeed a good case study for solutions journalism, which aims to elicit good governance by adopting journalism

practises covering not only problems found in society, but also successful solutions to those problems. Two fieldwork projects in Italy, in the cities of Casal di Principe and Genova, allow gathering data on the specific societal impact of reusing confiscated property—that could be shared and compared with data from other impacted areas and highlight the role that civil society plays in resolving complex societal issues. The pilot’s activities in the field involve residents of the areas impacted by organised crime, policymakers, apprentice journalists and scientific journalists.

“L’usage social des biens confisqués” blog and its existing media environment

URL address : <https://usbc.hypotheses.org/>

Pilot 3’s open electronic research notebook was launched in November 2021, and the blog’s main language is French. The editorial team of the blog includes the journalist and the independent researcher involved in the Pilot.

Hypotheses.org submission procedure asks for the fulfilment of a questionnaire that includes the project description and the authors affiliations, but it also asks some academic-centred questions such as classifying the blog according to two thematic indexes of disciplines. The questionnaire also asks to indicate which “type” of blog is suggested, providing a list where a “participatory research” or “citizen science” box is missing. This led to some confusion and misunderstanding at the beginning on the pilot’s team side, and they suggested some adjustments that may be implemented by the Hypotheses.org team for the application phase.

Among the WordPress themes preselected by the Hypotheses.org team they chose the Twenty Twenty One. As the home page, they choose to use the common blogs dynamic page, which gives access to the latest published article.

The Pilot 3 team uses the Hypotheses.org blog as a space for summarising and reporting about their research on the field once the fieldwork is concluded. Their fieldnotes, discussions and first hypothesis have been collected through a shared, though private, digital document. They also collected data in the form of recordings. The blog is a space to push forward the hypothesis and formulate intermediate analyses, in order to build the two separated final outputs of their joint research: a journalistic article series and an academic research article.

Project pilots partners, Cafébabel and Crim’HALT, have their own websites. A cross-media practice has been put into practice, connecting the same content on the Hypotheses.org and on the Crim’HALT website⁹. Provided that the journalist will write articles about social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia on Cafébabel media, which is a multilingual online magazine, and the researcher will write an article for a scientific journal, based on the fieldwork they lead together, a transmedia logic seems most appropriate for this project, and may help to build bridges between the three media: Cafébabel online magazine, Crim’HALT website and Hypotheses.org blog.

⁹ See Fabrice Rizzoli, “Bilan de la loi italienne permettant l’usage social des biens confisqués aux mafieux”, in L’usage social des biens confisqués à la mafia, 16 December 2021, <<https://usbc.hypotheses.org/25>>

Pilot 4: Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism

Pilot 4 project summary

Pilot 4 includes criminologists from [Crime&Tech](#), a spin-off company of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, and journalists from the investigative journalism association [IRPI](#).

The risk of corruption, collusion and inequality in civil society (e.g. in public procurement, tax collection or allocation of resources among citizens) results from complex and opaque corporate structures in the legitimate economy. Key anomalies in firms can flag high risks of corruption and financial crime, but there are few studies and practical tools to help police, investigative journalists and the civic society as a whole to monitor the transparency of ownership structures in Europe and assess related corruption risks. Crime&Tech provides investigative journalists at IRPI with instruments to analyse firms' data—specifically from case-studies, selected by the journalists—to identify high risks of corruption or high vulnerabilities. The project demonstrates how these tools can increase the impact of investigative journalism as well as builds a sustainable framework for sharing sensitive data. It involves practitioners in the legal and security fields and investigative journalists.

“The backstory” blog and its existing media environment

URL address : <https://thebackstory.hypotheses.org/>

Pilot 4's open electronic research notebook was launched in November 2021, and the blog's main language is Italian. The Pilot 4 core team is composed of IRPI journalists and Crime&Tech researchers. Together, they will write articles about the “behind the scenes” of the project they are leading.

Among the WordPress themes preselected by the Hypotheses.org team they chose the Twenty Twenty One. As the home page, they use the common blogs dynamic page, which features the latest published article.

Pilot 4 manages sensitive data, and works on private databases. Their Hypotheses.org blog is used to explain how they are reaching their forthcoming research results through the joint use of the tools provided by Crime&Tech and how researchers and journalists can collaborate on the common issues of corruption, collusion and inequality in civil society, thanks to a participatory research approach. They also address the issues of sharing sensitive research data between stakeholders of diverse professional fields.

Crime&Tech and IRPI have their own institutional websites, furthermore IRPI manages an online investigative media channel, IRPI Media¹⁰. A transmedia strategy could be developed bridging the Hypotheses.org blog and IRPI Media.

It is useful to note here that both Pilots 3 and Pilot 4 bring together researchers and journalists. The journalists involved in both pilots are accustomed to a wide variety of writing styles, are able to target a diversity of audiences, and master storytelling techniques fitted for diverse media

¹⁰ See <https://irpimedia.irpi.eu/>

formats. Their first question was indeed about the publishing format and publishing plan, in a result-oriented output perspective: which frequency of publishing? Which “adequate” text length? On the researchers’ side, it sounds normal to also report on the process leading to the results. It will be interesting to explore which kind of formats may arise from the encounter of these two editorial cultures—the journalistic and the academic one, in the same open space of an electronic research notebook on Hypotheses.org.

Pilot 5: Growing migrant knowledge. Contemporary and historical perspectives

Pilot 5 project summary

Pilot 5 gathers researchers from the [German Historical Institute Washington](#) and practitioners of the [Migrant Knowledge Network](#), and will involve lay citizens in one of the core activities of the pilot.

Migration challenges society on many levels, and solutions require systemic collaboration, which is not widely practised, between the many stakeholders (researchers, administrations, policy makers, educators, citizens and migrants themselves). This project brings together historical and comparative perspectives on migration through two distinct initiatives.

The first initiative, “Writing Across Borders: Narratives of Migration, 1800–1950”, engages lay citizens to work with a digital collection of correspondence sent from German-speaking lands to families and friends who migrated across the Atlantic. In these diaries and other “ego-documents,” migrants reflect on their journeys, their coping mechanisms and how the experience of migration changed them.

The second initiative, “Network Migrant Knowledge,” is a “practitioner in residence” program where researchers and practitioners (e.g. experts from governmental sectors and NGOs and activists of different backgrounds) concerned with historic and contemporary migration issues discuss “migrants as carriers and producers of knowledge.” Through this process, participants engage in transatlantic dialogue, develop an international perspective and help develop a concrete tool to build evidence-based policies that rely on collaborative research involving concerned citizens. It involves researchers, lay citizens, practitioners from governmental sectors and NGOs, activists and policymakers.

“Migrant connections” blog and its existing media environment

URL address : <https://migconn.hypotheses.org/>

The Pilot 5 activities are part of a larger research endeavour addressing the topic of migrant knowledge, building on three existing networks now blended through the unifying hub “[Migrant Connections](#)”. The blog “Migrant connections” complement this larger purpose, and the Pilot 5 activities will be a subsection of the blog. This open electronic research notebook was launched in November 2021, and the blog’s main language is English. The core editorial team is composed of the researchers from the German Historical Institute Washington, and other participants in the pilot activities will be invited to contribute to the blog.

Among the WordPress themes preselected by the Hypotheses.org team they chose the Twenty

Twenty One. As the home page, they use the common blogs dynamic page, which features the latest published article.

The pilot team and the citizen scientists involved in the project work on three corpora: letters, diaries and newspapers. The participants are active in transcribing and translating collections manually as well as through automated transcription processes. The culminating experience will be a symposium in which diary transcribers, machine-learning “trainers” and scholars from the “Migrant Knowledge” Network will gather together to learn how these collaborative steps are pointing towards new ways of doing research. They will present and discuss their research outcomes with experts from the “Migrant Knowledge” Network.

The blog will report about this research process and will serve for sharing an introduction of the sources and the collected diaries. One of the pilot team members will write on the blog and will encourage participants to express their experience, for instance through interview. The project and their Hypotheses.org blog is expected to continue beyond the COESO project timeframe.

Pilot 5 editorial team is already used for academic blogging and managing a diversity of digital data. Support may be given here in building consistent links between the Migrant Connection website and blog and in finding appropriate ways to get the citizens, involved in the pilot, actually *writing* about their findings in an academic blogging space—on top of contributing to the research activities.

Conclusion

Hypotheses.org is an international academic blogging platform dedicated to the social sciences and the humanities, gathering a community of researchers open to and experimenting with new forms of open scholarly communication. Besides COESO pilots’ blogs, Hypotheses.org already hosts blogs in support of participatory research and citizen science projects involving the social sciences and the humanities.

The first five pilots of the COESO project are autonomously managing their own open electronic notebook (blogs) on the platform, supported by the documentation provided by the Hypotheses.org team and by a dedicated community manager, focused on the specific needs of participatory research activities.

Blogs on Hypotheses.org have high outreach and a clear editorial policy, making them a particularly appropriate tool for research activities with social impact potential. They furthermore are a favourable space for experimenting with new forms of writing and rendering research processes and outputs. The contribution from non-academic stakeholders cannot be taken for granted and needs special attention for building appropriate support paths that take into account the specificities of participatory research projects.

Annex 1 : Screenshots of pilots' blogs

Screenshot of “Cidade (In)visível. Turismo e outras práticas quotidianas em Lisboa”
<https://civtur.hypotheses.org/>, 30th November 2021.

OPENEDITION SEARCH Q | Todo OpenEdition

Redatores Sobre o blog

Passeio por Santo António

08/11/2021
 Avenida da Liberdade,
 Freguesia de Santo
 António, Mapa, Passeio
 Deixe um comentário

Cidade (In)visível
 Passeio por Santo António
 Sábado, 23 de Outubro, 2021
 11h

Há uma cidade autêntica, há uma identidade de Lisboa? Como se ocupa o espaço público (ruas, passeios, esplanadas) na cidade? Quem são os habitantes? Há diferenças e os conflitos entre residentes e visitantes? O que compramos na cidade, quem compra e quem vende? Estas foram algumas das questões que nos colocámos a partir de uma primeira fase exploratória do projecto *Cidade (In)visível* e das conclusões do *workshop* realizado no passado 23 de Setembro. A partir daquelas questões orientadoras, decidimos organizar um *Passeio por Santo António* com os investigadores e associados da ZERO, com vista a observar e registar os efeitos do turismo na vida quotidiana nesta freguesia de Lisboa. Acreditamos que, ao percorrer o espaço público em conjunto, a experiência do passeio permite assinalar diferentes dimensões da vida urbana quotidiana. Observar quem usa, habita e reclama certos espaços públicos, em que condições ambientais se encontram, como as ruas e fachadas dos edifícios reflectem a vida social de quem os habita, o que vendem as lojas abertas, permite registar relações sociais e outros fenómenos sociais urbanos. Toma-se assim o acto de caminhar em conjunto como base de uma metodologia de investigação colaborativa de cariz etnográfico.

Pesquisar ...

Um blogue de investigação colaborativa no âmbito do projeto europeu COESO – Collaborative Engagement for Societal Issues.

O projeto “Cidade (In)visível. Turismo e outras práticas quotidianas em Lisboa” observa práticas turísticas a uma escala micro, documentando e analisando situações de conflitos, mediações, processos de acordo, os quais moldam a vida urbana.

CATEGORIAS

- Anti-turismo (1)

Screenshot of “Dansophie/Dancing philosophy”
<https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/>, 30th November 2021.

Dansophie/Dancing philosophy

Projet de recherche participative dans le cadre du projet européen COESO – Collaborative Engagement for Societal Issues

Crédits À propos

Dancing philosophy à Barcelone

stefaniaferrando
 12/11/2021
 Barcelone, Carla Lonzi
 Laisser un commentaire

Les deux écrans – Cosetta et Stefania en direct au séminaire Diferència sexual una ontologia pràctica? (3 novembre 2021)

La collaboration entre Cosetta et moi est radicale : on relève le défi d’aller jusqu’aux racines de nos pratiques philosophique et chorégraphique, ainsi que des paroles qui s’y incarnent.

Ainsi, pendant les semaines de résidence à Wissous, je suis montée sur scène. Il s’agissait de questionner le langage philosophique à partir d’un travail sur le corps et le contact avec le langage chorégraphique.

En retour, il était important de proposer à Cosetta d’intervenir dans un séminaire de recherche. Une occasion formidable s’est présentée : j’ai été invitée au séminaire **Diferència sexual una ontologia pràctica?**, organisé par Teresa Hoogeveen, Alina Mierlus et Andrea Ugalde (Seminari Filosofia i Gènere; ADHUC–Centre de Recerca Teoria, Gènere, Sexualitat; Màster d’Estudis de Dones, Gènere i Ciutadania – Universitat de Barcelona).

Recherche...

MOTS-CLEFS

Barcelone Carla Lonzi COESO
 danse Hegel philosophie
 psychanalyse recherche citoyenne

CATÉGORIES

• Uncategorized (9)

ARCHIVES

• novembre 2021 (1)
 • octobre 2021 (7)
 • septembre 2021 (1)

PHILOSOPHIE – CALENDRA

- La phénoménologie critique après Merleau-Ponty
- Dieu(x) et numérique(s)
- Aesthetics and Critique IV : Contemporaneity
- Penser le débat sur l’anthropocène avec Merleau-Ponty
- Déclinaisons du risque
- On Hinterlands and Homelands
- Histoires, méthodes et actualités des savoirs situés féministes
- Discours d’Afrique : le genre en question
- D’autres imaginaires : approches postcoloniales de l’Anthropocène
- Performance

Screenshot of “Usage social biens confisqués à la mafia”
<https://usbc.hypotheses.org/>, 13th December 2021.

USAGE SOCIAL BIENS CONFISQUÉS À LA MAFIA
recherche et journalisme de solution

Crédits À propos

Apprendre de l'expérience de l'usage social de biens confisqués en Italie, à travers le journalisme de solution et l'étude socio-politique

La coopérative Al di là dei sogni (“Au delà des rêves”) à Sessa Aurunca en Campanie sur un terrain confisqué à la mafia napolitaine, @Dorcadie @Coeso juillet 2021

L'usage social des biens confisqués à la mafia à l'épreuve du journalisme de solution (english version) Pourquoi allons-nous travailler sur l'antimafia sociale ? En travaillant depuis des années sur le sujet, Fabrice Rizzoli garde l'impression que l'étude des mafias italiennes fait encore l'objet de nombreuses approximations de la part des experts, ceux de l'école de... Poursuivre la lecture de

Screenshot of “The Backstory”

<https://thebackstory.hypotheses.org/>, 30th November 2021.

The screenshot shows the Hypotheses website interface. At the top left is the Hypotheses logo. At the top right, there is a search bar with the text 'OPENEDITION SEARCH Q' and a magnifying glass icon, followed by 'All OpenEdition' and a grid icon. The main content area has a dark background. On the left, it says 'THE BACKSTORY' and 'Un percorso condiviso tra ricerca e giornalismo'. On the right, there are links for 'Crediti' and 'A proposito'. The title 'The Backstory' is centered in a large font. Below the title, there is a paragraph of text: 'Questa pubblicazione si propone di condividere esperienze e modalità di collaborazione tra il mondo accademico e quello del giornalismo investigativo, in particolare nel settore della ricerca sui fenomeni della criminalità mafiosa ed economica'. At the bottom, it says 'Pubblicato 25/11/2021' and 'Etichettato come Uncategorized'.

Screenshot of “Migrant Connections”
<https://migconn.hypotheses.org/>, 30th November 2021.

OPENEDITION SEARCH Q | All OpenEdition

MIGRANT CONNECTIONS

Migrant Connections

How do Citizen Humanities projects develop? And how have such endeavors changed over the course of the last decades? One of the research areas of the German Historical Institute Washington focuses on the intersection of Digital History and German Migration to the United States. “Migrant Connections” will be launched in the fall of 2021 as... [Continue reading](#)

Published November 10, 2021
Categorized as [Allgemein](#)

Annex 2 : Screenshots of pilots' media

Screenshot of Café Babel

<https://cafebabel.com/en/>, 23th November 2021. Pilot 3 partner.

Screenshot of IRPI MEDIA

<https://irpimedia.irpi.eu/>, 23th November 2021. Pilot 4 partner.

The screenshot shows the homepage of the IRPI MEDIA website. At the top left, there is a black box with the text "Investigative Reporting Project Italy". To the right of this box, the words "IRPI MEDIA" are written in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. Below the header, there is a red horizontal line. On the left side of this line, the word "MENU" is followed by a small red icon of a magnifying glass. On the right side, the word "DONA" is written in red. Below the red line, there are three main content areas. The first is a large image of an industrial facility with the headline "Dall'acqua al sangue" in white text. The second is a smaller image of a building with the headline "Brogli elettorali 2018 alla circoscrizione Estero, il senatore Cario resta in carica" in white text. The third is a dark image of an airport with the headline "La strana storia dell'aeroporto di Parma" in white text.

Screenshot of “Migrant Knowledge”

<https://migrantknowledge.org/>, 23th November 2021. Pilot 5 partner.

